

INSTRUMENTS FOR STUDENT VERIFICATION AND ASSESSMENT OF HIS EMOTIONAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STATE DURING REMOTE WORK**Uymin A.***Senior Lecturer**(Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin)*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327249>**Abstract**

The article discusses the use of neural networks to verify a student and assess his emotional and psychological state during remote work, using the RemoteTopology software platform as an example. As part of the implementation of projects of the WorldSkills Russia movement

Keywords: to RemoteTopology; remote work; proctoring; verification; worldskills.

Since 2019, due to the problems of COVID-19, the problem of distance education has come to the fore. This problem is considered in detail in this work [1]. In particular, emphasis is placed on the lack of experience in the use of mass distance educational technologies and the impact of their use on the emotional and psychological state of the student. Educational organizations are faced with the problem of implementing the educational process, as well as conducting intermediate and final certification in a remote format. This problem is complex in view of the need for professional organizations to obtain an independent assessment of qualifications and participate in ratings, which affects the overall psychological background of work. The work [2] considers the issue of stability of results in the preparation and participation of students and graduates in various events, aimed at assessing qualifications according to the WorldSkills methodology. The tools of the WorldSkills movement allow conducting mass educational programs, as well as assessing qualifications based on the results of training [3]. In [2], the issues of applying this technique within a particular region are considered. It also focuses on performance. This work covers 2019 and 2020, when most of the activities within the framework of the intermediate and final certification are in a remote format. At the same time, the issues of assessing the emotional and psychological state of a student during remote work, as well as the influence of his condition on the intermediate and final certification conducted in a remote format, were not considered. In the classical version of passing exams, the student works with people, receiving feedback from teachers, masters of industrial training, examiners or supervisors. It does not remain alone with hardware and software. In the case of working remotely, the issue of proctoring arises, which is discussed in detail in [4]. The paper notes that proctoring allows you to increase the reliability and reliability of the results of intermediate and final certification in a remote format. Proctors, like the exam coordinators in the classroom, monitor the process to ensure that participants follow the rules when taking online exams (complete assignments on their own and do not use external materials and additional resources). At the same time, the influence of the human factor, both positive - the effect of presence, and negative - the effect of the warden, is not described in

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1) Assess the level of independence in completing tasks - determining the level of "honesty" of the examinee

2) Make an assessment of the emotional and psychological state of the examinee in order to determine the most comfortable options for implementing the remote format of working with the examinee.

This article will discuss which educational institutions consistently win at the level of the Russian Federation, which competencies implemented in the Sverdlovsk region are the most stable in obtaining prize-winning places, whether the frequency of leadership changes and the total duration of the leader's work in this position affect the effectiveness of the participation of an educational organization in the Championships, how the dynamics of getting prize-winning places has changed in the period from 2013 to 2020, how many specialties of the TOP-50 are the most effective in the region, how many specialties included in the list of Worldskills Hi-Tech Championships are the most effective in the region, which only a few will be able to solve on their own, without attracting third-party organizations offering proctoring services. And these are additional financial investments not planned in the budget.

Most modern remote work systems, including those using proctoring tools, allow you to very accurately determine a specific user, which is achieved by transferring key information, such as login / password and video audio images. Proctoring systems, both automated, using artificial intelligence, and non-automated - a person, allow you to monitor basic parameters, such as head rotation, eye direction, and acoustic data. In this case, these solutions have conditional accuracy [5].

In modern solutions, the question arises of using behavioral biometrics, which, on the one hand, will allow you to identify the user, and, on the other hand, will assess his emotional and psychological state based on independent metrics. The use of these tools will allow you to build a neural network to process unique behavioral characteristics, such as keyboard handwriting, mouse movements, mouse button presses, switching between windows, etc.

Within the framework of the project [6], a module for automatic proctoring and assessment of the participant's condition is being developed. The learner is authorized in the system, and then in the course of work, he interacts with the neural network, which monitors his work. The system input receives data during the performance of laboratory work, practical work, and intermediate or final certification. All these types of actions are a set of commands, work in a graphical interface, work in command line mode with virtual or real equipment through the platform RemoteTopology. Interface view Fig 1.

Figure 1 - RemoteTopology Interface

The task of the neural network, at the time of learning, is to determine the order of actions of users: the actions of the student with the keyboard and mouse, and the effectiveness of the check. The system should determine the individual "handwriting", the performance of the work, to verify the trainee throughout the work. The system should distinguish between three levels of the emotional and psychological state of the student. The first is the operating mode: the calm execution of the task, taking into account the time limit, the reachability of the technology block in accordance with WSSS [7]. The second mode is disturbing work: the execution of work that leads to a result, but requires an additional number of steps, is not synchronized in time, there is no systematic execution. The third mode is a panic attack, when actions do not lead to the achievement of results, do not provide a systematic approach to solving the problem. These modes are possible in combination, and the platform will help to identify those parts of the task that most negatively affect the trainees. This will allow you to adjust the methods of conducting training, intermediate or final certification.

The input data received by RemoteTopology can be represented as the following functionality:

$$X_i = N_i[x_1(t), x_2(t), x_3(t) \dots x_n(t)], \quad (1)$$

where, $x_1(t)$, $x_2(t)$, $x_3(t) \dots x_n(t)$ are the parameters of the individual signature of the i -th student.

Expression (1) is an individual manner of performing work on the user's platform. When defining a user, i.e. its individual signature, it is possible for the system

to make decisions about whether the user who started working or worked before is now in the system, as well as determining the level of his state on each task.

It is necessary to introduce the concept of determining the system efficiency assessment, which is defined as

$$Q_x = S_r / S_w, \quad (2)$$

where, S_r is the number of correct solutions of the system. S_w is the number of all solutions of the system.

It is necessary to introduce the concept of erroneous decisions of the system:

$$Q_e = S_e / S_w, \quad (3)$$

where, S_e is the number of erroneous decisions of the system. S_w is the number of all solutions of the system.

During the data collection, information was obtained from a focus group of 30 people, age 18-22, gender M - 18, F - 12, the work was carried out within the framework of disciplines in network technologies, in college in the 2022 academic year.

On Fig. 2 shows the frequency analysis of mouse shift phase, mouse shift angle, mouse shift speed. Fig. 2a is a benchmark of student N's work state, Fig. 2b shows work in the state of laboratory work, according to this graph, it is possible to determine the elements that cause peaks - difficulties corresponding to the state of discomfort. The Z-axis determines the time sampling, the Y-axis determines the normalized value of the manipulator movement, the X-axis determines the normalized manipulator movement speed.

Figure 2 - Graphical representation

The task is complex, both in terms of determining the reliability of the fact that the user independently performs the work, and in terms of determining his state when performing the work. This solution is currently being implemented as part of the RemoteTopology project. The introduction of such a solution will improve the quality of educational materials, and update and more fully develop blocks of practical and examination tasks that form the largest number of "uncomfortable" situations during remote work. The solution is aimed at increasing the efficiency of the use of computer technology, in terms of refusing human proctoring, refusing to monitor the student and improving the quality of feedback, both for the student and for the developer of materials, teacher, master of industrial training, examiner.

References:

1. Skrypnikova N. N. The future of education: total distance or total rejection of it? // Professional education and labor market. - 2020. - № 2. - pages 58-59.
2. Uymin, A. G. Development of professional training taking into account the standards of "Worldskills Russia" / A. G. Uymin // Bulletin of Pedagogical Sciences. - 2021. - № 1. - pages 42-51.

3. Ishkil'dina S.A., Lukin A.A., Kruchinina A.A. Problems of retraining and advanced training of personnel according to WorldSkills standards // Innovations and investments. 2020. №1. - 2020, - pages 94-97.

4. Nazarova Lyudmila Ivanovna, Siman Alexey Sergeevich, Lyamina Irina Mazhitovna, Koloskova Galina Aleksandrovna Organization of proctoring in distance learning for students of an agricultural university // Agroengineering. 2020. № 4 (98). - 2020, - pages 72-77.

5. Tymoshchuk E.A., Tymoshchuk A.S., Tyagi R. Coercion to Distance as a Crisis and New Opportunities // Archon. 2021. № 1 (22). — 2021, — S. 95-101

6. Certificate of state registration of the computer program No. 2021619990 Russian Federation. RemoteTopology-Authorization Module : № 2021613424 : App. 03/09/2021 : publ. 06/21/2021 / A. G. Uymin, S. V. Lyubkin.

7. Fakhrutdinova Guzalia Zhevdyatovna, Gerasimova Evgenia Olegovna, Zayachuk Tatyana Vladimirovna The history of the formation of the WORLDSKILLS RUSSIA movement // Medicine. Sociology. Philosophy. Applied research. 2020. №6. — 2020, — pages 105-108